

Statistical analysis plan 5 years follow-up

**Treat Early Arthralgia to Reverse or Limit
Impending Exacerbation to Rheumatoid arthritis**

A randomized clinical trial in recent-onset arthralgia patients that are suspect to progress to rheumatoid arthritis evaluating the efficacy of intervention with a single dose of IM corticosteroids and methotrexate

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Timing of writing Statistical Analysis Plan 5 years follow-up

This Statistical Analysis Plan for the analysis of 5 years follow-up data of the TREAT EARLIER trial was written and submitted to the local Medical Ethical Committee Leiden Den Haag Delft (CME LDD) and uploaded at an EU Open Research Repository (zenodo.org) before the last patient completed the 5 year follow-up duration and before the data was cleaned and locked. Interim analysis was performed at 4 years follow-up on one of the primary endpoints[1], see below, this did not affect data collection up to year 5 and the analyses described in this Statistical Analysis Plan.

Protocol versions

The initial trial protocol was submitted as Trial NL4599 at trial register and the protocol was approved by the local Medical Ethical Committee of the Leiden University Medical Center on January 12, 2015. After amendments for increasing the sample size (2018) and the addition of an explorative endpoint (course of MRI-detected inflammation; 2019), in 2020, a change was made (February 25, 2020) to extend the follow-up duration of the study by 3 years, in addition to the first 2 years, resulting in a total follow-up duration of 5 years. The final version of the protocol was previously published[2] and included as appendix to [3].

A statistical analysis plan covering the first 2 trial years has been written and submitted to the local Medical Ethical Committee in June 2021, before the randomization code was broken. The results of these 2 years data have been published elsewhere.[3]

The present Statistical Analysis Plan describes the analyses that are planned for the 5 years data.

Background

For a full background of the trial we refer to the study protocol that was previously published.[2, 3] In short, Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is characterized by chronic inflammation of joints, particularly of hands and feet. Within the phase of clinically evident RA, it has been clearly shown that early intervention is associated with better long-term outcomes.[4]

Currently, the earliest diagnosis of RA can be made if physical examination displays joint swelling (i.e. clinically apparent inflammatory arthritis). Importantly, at the time of diagnosis, the immune processes have already matured, thereby chronicity is established and patients require longstanding treatment with Disease Modifying Antirheumatic Drugs (DMARDs).[5] Since ca. 2012, several observational studies have shown that subclinical joint inflammation can be detected using advanced imaging modalities, e.g. MRI, before RA becomes clinically apparent.[6-8]

Based on the observations that the time to intervention determined the efficacy of the intervention in RA, and the fact that subclinical joint inflammation can now be detected in a phase that precedes clinically apparent arthritis, we hypothesized that intervention with RA in this 'preclinical'/at-risk phase of clinically suspect arthralgia (CSA) and subclinical joint inflammation is effective in reducing progression to clinically apparent inflammatory arthritis and RA and in reducing the disease burden of people in this risk stage.

The TREAT EARLIER trial is a placebo-controlled, randomized, proof-of-concept study that tests this hypothesis.

The objectives and analyses for the 5-year follow-up are largely similar to those for the 2-year follow-up and include the following considerations:

1. We hypothesize that a 1-year course of treatment in this risk phase induces long-lasting beneficial effects.
2. Important known risk factors are accounted for in the analyses. The study was designed in 2014 based on available knowledge at the time, which, in the field of arthralgia at-risk for RA and classified RA, has since expanded resulting in two important insights. First, increasing evidence from risk factor, observational, and translational studies suggests that the development of anti-citrullinated protein antibody (ACPA)-positive RA is different from ACPA-negative RA. We hypothesize that these pathophysiological differences may influence the efficacy of interventions performed in patients who are in the trajectory of RA development. Second, as risk stratification for people with CSA was non-existing in 2014, the trial was designed with a known risk (PPV) of 31% to develop RA; this risk could not be further differentiated at that time. This uniform attribution of risk can blur preventive effects in the presence of actual risk heterogeneity (so-called 'clinicostatistical tragedy').^[9] Since a prediction model for CSA is now present, we will now incorporate risk stratification to analyse subgroups at increased risk. Patients who, in retrospect, were at low risk for RA at the time of inclusion in the trial will be excluded from analyses.

Aims

1. To determine the efficacy of intervention with antirheumatic treatment in the risk phase of CSA with subclinical joint inflammation in preventing or delaying the progression to RA during a 5-year follow-up, in ACPA-positive and ACPA-negative individuals at increased risk for RA.

2. To determine the efficacy of intervention with antirheumatic treatment in the risk phase of CSA with subclinical joint inflammation in reducing the severity of the burden during a 5-year follow-up, in ACPA-positive and ACPA-negative individuals at increased risk for RA.

Study population

A two-level definition was used to identify patients that were prone to develop RA. First, patients needed to have arthralgia that is suspect to progress to RA according to the treating rheumatologist (CSA, as identified by the clinical expertise of treating rheumatologists) and second, patients should have a scan of hands and feet made on a 1.5T extremity MRI scanner showing local subclinical joint inflammation.

1) Clinically suspect arthralgia (CSA)

The identification of CSA was performed by rheumatologists using pattern recognition, i.e. clinical assessment. It is based on information provided by history taking and physical examination (clinical symptoms and signs). Per definition, CSA was not present if patients presented with clinical arthritis or if another explanation for the symptoms (e.g. osteoarthritis, fibromyalgia) was more likely. Abnormal results of laboratory examination (acute phase reactants, auto-antibodies) were not required to identify CSA. Moreover, auto-antibody status was generally not known at first presentation to the rheumatology outpatient clinic because, in line with Dutch GP-guidelines, auto-antibodies were rarely determined in primary care in our region.[10] Hence, identification of CSA was based on the expertise of rheumatologists. We have previously demonstrated that the clinical expertise is accurate in differentiating CSA patients from all arthralgia patients (odds ratio of 55, sensitivity 80% specificity 93%).[11] Fulfilment of the EULAR definition of arthralgia suspicious for progression to RA was not required as the trial was designed in 2014 and this definition was developed in 2016.[12]

2) MRI detected subclinical inflammation in small joints

Subclinical inflammation was identified using 1.5T contrast-enhanced MRI of metacarpophalangeal (MCP)-, wrist and metatarsophalangeal (MTP)-joints. Presence of subclinical inflammation was defined in relation to MRI-data obtained from symptom-free controls from the general population. At the time of writing of the protocol in 2014, the scanning of the persons from the general population was in progress, but results were unknown. As reported in 2016, MRIs of 193 symptom-free persons from the general

population revealed that MRI-detected inflammation is present, in low degrees, especially at older ages and at preferential locations.[13] In addition the findings differed for the inflammatory features synovitis, bone marrow edema and tenosynovitis. Based on the MRIs of the symptom-free persons reference tables were made for the different inflammatory features, the different joints and subsequently divided in three age-categories (18-40, 40-60 and >60 years). An MRI was considered positive for subclinical inflammation when two raters independently scored inflammation (synovitis, bone marrow edema or tenosynovitis) in ≥ 1 location that was present in <5% of the symptom-free persons in the same age-category at the same location.[6, 14] We have shown that use of a reference population resulted in a substantial reduction of false-positive results, without influencing the sensitivity.[15] In addition, we have demonstrated that the presence of subclinical inflammation in patients with CSA is associated with a risk to develop clinically apparent inflammatory arthritis during the next year of 31%.[16]

The MRIs from all patients that were screened for this trial were made on the same MRI-scanner with the same protocol as the symptom-free controls. All MRIs were independently scored by 2 readers blinded for any clinical data. All MRI readers had a training period of 4-6 months, scored hundreds of MRIs and showed a reliable score before being allowed to score the MRIs for screening for this study. After the training period, the within and between reader ICC was regularly assessed.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria

1. Age ≥ 18 years
2. Patients without clinically apparent arthritis but with arthralgia of small hand or feet joints of recent-onset (<1-year) that according to the rheumatologist is suspect to be an early presentation of RA (this symptom complex is called CSA)
3. Extremity MRI positive for subclinical inflammation
4. Ability and willingness to give written informed consent and to comply with the requirements of the study protocol

Exclusion criteria

1. Symptoms or signs making diagnoses other than RA more likely. These are amongst others >6 tender points or presence of Heberden or Bouchard nodes (if another disease is considered to be more likely, CSA is precluded)
2. Presence of, or history of, clinically apparent arthritis (this precluded CSA)

3. Previous or current treatment with disease modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs) or corticosteroids (this precluded CSA)
4. Contra indications for MRI: certain metal implants, pacemakers, GFR<30 ml/min
5. Pregnancy or the wish to become pregnant, breast feeding
6. Bone marrow hypoplasia
7. Elevated hepatic enzyme levels (ASAT, ALAT >3 times normal value)
8. Serum creatinine level >150 umol/l or estimated clearance of <60%
9. Serious infections such as hepatitis, pyelonephritis in the past three months or chronic infectious disease such as chronic chest infections with bronchiectasis

Intervention

In this double-blind randomized controlled trial (RCT), patients were randomized to two arms in a 1:1 ratio. In the first arm patients received one intramuscular (IM) glucocorticoid injection (120mg methylprednisolone) followed by 12-months of methotrexate (MTX), in the other arm patients received a placebo IM injection and placebo tablets. Short term steroids combined with rapid escalation of MTX to a dose of 25mg/week is the recommended first line treatment of RA (EULAR recommendations).[17] In line with these recommendations for the treatment of RA, trial medication was escalated to 10 tablets/week (in the verum group corresponding to MTX 25mg/week), if tolerated. No other glucocorticoid or DMARD interventions were allowed during the trial, unless patients had reached the primary endpoint and proceeded to open label DMARD therapy. Open label folic acid supplementation (5mg/week) was added in all patients during the first year, this dosage is in line with the national Dutch guidelines of MTX use.[18]

Concomitant treatment with analgesics such as acetaminophen and/or non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) was allowed for all patients, except for 24-hours before MRI scans. After 1-year of treatment with trial medication, patients were followed for another 4-years.

Randomization and blinding

The local pharmacist of the LUMC provided the trial medications and took care of randomization, using a block randomization scheme with a fixed block size of ten. Scientific staff, rheumatologists and patients remained blind to treatment allocation, also when the primary endpoint was reached and patients were treated with open label DMARD therapy according to routine care. Unblinding occurred after all patients had completed 2-years

follow-up and all 2-years data had been cleaned and locked. At the moment of unblinding, 44% of participants had already completed the total 5 year follow-up. Information about treatment arm allocation was then sent to study participants but not to treating rheumatologists.

Follow-up

Year 0-2

Participants were followed with 4-monthly intervals for 2-years. In case of an increase in symptoms in between two study visits, an additional visit to the rheumatologist took place in between the scheduled visits. In case clinically detectable arthritis was present at any visit, an additional visit was scheduled after 2-weeks to evaluate whether the clinical arthritis was persistent (and not-self-limiting). If a participant developed this, usual treatment was indicated. Patients then left the protocolized study follow-up and were treated under usual rheumatology care (according to the existing treatment recommendation for RA).

Year 3-5

Follow-up was included in routine care, with the decision on number of visits left to the treating rheumatologist and patient. It was recommended to treat in accordance with existing EULAR recommendations for early arthritis and RA; in line with these recommendations DMARDs were only allowed after clinically apparent arthritis / RA had developed. DMARD-use in the stage of CSA was considered as 'forbidden'; its frequency was collected. Electronic patient files were examined for all visits that took place in the years 3-5. Joint counts and use of DMARDs (including corticosteroid tablets or injections) were extracted to verify the endpoint. For patients that did not develop RA, it was evaluated whether information in the medical files were up-to-date and whether data was not missing e.g. due to participants switching hospitals. To this end all participants were phoned after 5-years years of follow-up to verify their status with respect to having developed the endpoint (development of RA) and to verify the treating rheumatologist (in order to assess the appropriate medical records). This was done to ensure completeness of the follow-up data. Upon 5-years follow-up, questionnaires were repeated.

Overview of collected data:

	Year 0-2							Year 3-5
	0-12-months: trial medication				12-24-months: no DMARDs			24-60-months: no DMARDs, visits in regular care
Month	0	4	8	12	16	20	24	60
Informed consent	X							X
RA-development		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
SJC-66	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
TJC-68	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
DAS44	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Physical examination	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Hand function tests	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Routine lab (safety and disease monitoring)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Questionnaires ^a	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
HAQ								
SF36								
B-IPQ								
EuroQoL								
WPAI								
RAI helplessness subscale								
iMTA								
Life satisfaction scale								
VAS morning stiffness, pain, global health and fatigue	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Hands and feet X- rays	X	X		X			X	
MRI	X	X		X			X	
Serum storage	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
DNA	X							
RNA	X	X	X	X			X	
Adverse events review	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Compliance and concomitant drug diary	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Diary on intermittent (co)morbidities	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Review medical files (SJC, diagnosis, DAS, DMARD-use)								X ^b

^a in all participants at every 4 months until the persistent clinically apparent arthritis/RA has developed (during 0-2 years); and in all individuals at year 5.

^bfor the whole period until 60 months. The number of visits is left to the treating rheumatologist. The mentioned data of all visits that occurred until 60 months are collected.

Endpoints

Primary endpoints

In line with the objectives of the trial, the primary endpoints are:

1. Development of RA. This is defined as clinically apparent inflammatory arthritis, with a clinical diagnosis of RA by the treating rheumatologist and either persistence during ≥ 2 weeks or prompt DMARD-initiation.
2. Burden of disease expressed in physical functioning (Health Assessment Questionnaire Disability Index (HAQ-DI, range 0-3)).

The primary endpoint development of RA can be considered to mainly reflect the perspective of rheumatologists. The other primary endpoint (physical functioning) focuses on the benefit from the patients' perspective. Patients have indicated that the burden of RA is best expressed by assessing the domains independence (functioning, workability) and symptoms such as pain.[19] Moreover, patients with CSA have indicated that not only RA-prevention, but also sustained improvement of the disease burden is a relevant treatment goal in the CSA-phase.[20] In addition, the limitations in physical functioning in the risk phase of CSA are as severe as in the phase of classified RA.[21]

Secondary endpoints to further assess disease duration

Other patient reported outcomes (PROs) that are interrelated with physical functioning but for which no composite measure exists will be evaluated:

- Pain (visual analogue scale (VAS), range 0-100),
- Morning stiffness (VAS, range 0-100).
- Work productivity: Assessed with the Work productivity and impairment scale (WPAI).

Explorative endpoints

- o Resolution of CSA. This is an endpoint that was not assessed in the 0-2 year data, but can now be assessed with longer follow-up. Resolution of the risk status of CSA reflects the best possible outcome. It is defined as achieving VAS pain ≤ 20 and VAS morning stiffness ≤ 20 and maintaining these VAS values in the subsequent follow-up visit (with minimal 4 months in between). By definition, developing clinically apparent arthritis precluded achieving resolution of CSA.
- o Measures of severity of RA within the patients that developed RA. This concerns an evaluation that is also new compared to the data collected before (2-year data). According to the study protocol 0-2 years, the study visits were stopped as soon as this endpoint and a regular treatment indication occurred. In the data up to 5 years,

data were collected from the medical record of the people who developed RA until the 5-year time point. The disease course of RA is measured in two ways: 1) the percentage of patients in DAS (disease activity score) remission at 12 months disease duration. This was defined as $DAS_{28} < 2.6$ 12 months after RA diagnosis. And 2) achieving DMARD-free remission. This is defined as complete discontinuation of DMARDS (including corticosteroids) without the occurrence of clinical arthritis (swollen joints as defined by the rheumatologist) for at least 6 months thereafter. For example, if a patient stopped all DMARDS and then developed clinical arthritis again after e.g. 4 months, this outcome would not be achieved.

- Quality of life: Short Form-36 (SF-36) (range 0-100), EuroQol 5D-5level (EQ-5D-5L) (per item, range 1-5), and VAS score (range 0-100)
- Health appraisal: Brief Illness perception questionnaire short (B-IPQ) (per item, range 0-10), Rheumatology Attitudes Index (RAI) helplessness subscale (range 5-25)
- Global assessment (VAS, range 0-10))
- Fatigue (VAS, range 0-100)
- Cost-efficacy measurement: iMTA

Analysis population

Intention-to-treat population

The intention-to-treat (ITT)-population will consist of all randomized patients. The ITT-population will form the primary analysis population of the study, and will be used for all primary and secondary efficacy endpoints.

Per-protocol population

The per-protocol (PP)-population will consist of all patients meeting the study entry criteria:

- who completed follow-up,
- who after randomization did not discontinue the study medication within the first two months and who in the first year, or up to a primary endpoint in this period, have used ≥ 8 study tablets/week for at least 80% of the time,
- who used no forbidden medication (no systemic or intra-articular steroids or DMARDS prescribed by rheumatologists outside the study protocol) during the total follow-up period.

A MTX dose of ≥ 20 mg/week has been shown to provide optimal efficacy in RA.[22-24] Also the updated EULAR recommendations for the management of rheumatoid arthritis (2019

update) refers to 20mg (or 25mg) per week as the optimal therapeutic dose.[25] Therefore a dose of ≥ 8 study tablets/week was incorporated in the definition of the PP-population.

The PP-analysis will thus only include patients who strictly adhered to the protocol and had no forbidden DMARDs during the total 5 years of follow-up. This means that the PP-population is the same as that analysed in the 0-2 year data, except that it also excludes participants who used prohibited DMARDs in the last 3 years of study. The PP-analysis provides an estimate of the 'true efficacy' of the MTX intervention although it may not represent the real-life situation and may be subject to selection bias.

Stratification and restriction based on risk factors

Analyses will be stratified according to ACPA-status because of the evidence that ACPA-positive and ACPA-negative RA have differences in underlying pathophysiology.[4, 26, 27] ACPA status, determined at baseline, is defined as anti-CCP2 ≥ 7 U/mL (EliA CCP, Phadia, the Netherlands))

Additionally, only patients with increased risk will be included in the analyses (restriction). Risk will be estimated using the prediction model of Matthijssen et al., which was developed in an independent CSA population[28] and shown accurate.[1, 3] The model consists of 4 variables (ACPA, rheumatoid factor, two variables on subclinical joint inflammation severity) for which 1 or 2 points each can be obtained. The total score ranges from 0-6 and risk for developing clinically apparent inflammatory arthritis is plotted in the figure below. Patients with 0 or 1 point were, in retrospect, found to be at low risk at the time of inclusion and will not be included in the analyses.

Figure with prediction model for CSA patients from Matthijssen et al (Ann Rheum Dis, 2020).[28]

Figure 1. Kaplan Meier curves on inflammatory arthritis development stratified for number of points based on LASSO regression. Legend: Points were based on the regression coefficients yielded by Cox LASSO-regression. 2 points were assigned for the risk factors ACPA-positivity and >2 locations of subclinical inflammation and 1 point was assigned for RF-positivity and presence of MCP-extensor peritendinitis.

Therefore, two groups will be studied: ACPA-positive participants at increased risk and ACPA-negative participants at increased risk. This allows to study the effect of intervention in the development of ACPA-positive RA and ACPA-negative RA.

Statistical methods

All categorical data will be summarized with frequency counts and percentages. Continuous variables will be summarized using the number of patients with corresponding mean, standard deviation (SD) in case of (approximate) normal distributions. Otherwise, median and 25th/75th percentile will be presented. Summary data will be calculated using the ITT-population; exceptions from this will be noted in the Table footnotes.

Analyses of primary endpoints

All analyses will follow the intention-to-treat principle. All efficacy analyses will be presented by a point estimate of the difference between the treatment groups, with a 95% confidence interval. The two primary endpoints will be corrected for multiple testing; P-values below 0.025 ($p < 0.025$) will therefore be considered statistically significant.

Development of RA. The primary analysis will be time to the development of this endpoint, visually depicted using arthritis-free survival using the Kaplan-Meier method, analyzed using log rank tests to test statistical significance (p-value) and Cox regression to quantify the effect (effect size with confidence interval) during 60-months follow-up. The proportional hazard assumption will be checked graphically (Kaplan-Meier, log-minus-log plot). Any patients that drop-out from the study will be censored at the point of drop-out/time of last contact. Patients that did not consent with the second part of the trial (3-5 years) will be censored at 2 years follow-up. No adjustments will be made.

Burden of CSA over time, expressed as physical functioning. A linear mixed model will be used to assess the difference over 60-months follow-up between the treatment groups. A random intercept will be used to model the repeated measurements. Model assumptions will be checked graphically by inspection of residuals. If a model adding a random slope can be fitted robustly, interpretation will be based on that model. Robustness will be evaluated based on correlation structure of parameter estimates and random effects, residuals and model convergence. Effect size, 95% confidence interval and p-value will be reported.

The ACPA-negative and ACPA-positive groups will be assessed by a gate-keeping analysis, by first testing the ACPA-negative group and if this is significant the ACPA-positive group will

be tested at the alpha level mentioned above ($p < 0.025$). This order is based on an evaluation of sample size and statistical power: evaluation at the 2-years horizon revealed a low number of ACPA-positive individuals at risk at 24 months ($n=3$ and 6 per arm) with an almost similar event rate at 24 months,[3] while recent analyses of the ACPA-negative group with increased risk showed higher patient numbers at the 2-year timepoint ($n= 31$ and 23 per arm).[1] The gatekeeping procedure therefore takes into account the low power in the ACPA-positive group, giving preference to the ACPA-negative group with higher sample size.

Analyses of secondary endpoints

The secondary endpoints are expected to be related to the primary endpoint physical functioning. Because of this relation, the coherence between the effects of the PROs will be included in the interpretation. Statistical tests (p -values) will be used sparingly to express effects. Linear mixed models will be used to assess the difference in PROs over 60-months follow-up between the treatment groups. The models will be similar as described above. A random intercept will be used to model the dependence of the repeated measurements. Model assumptions will be checked graphically by inspection of residuals. If a model adding a random slope can be fitted robustly, interpretation will be based on that model. Robustness will be evaluated based on correlation structure of parameter estimates and random effects, residuals and model convergence.

Analyses of explorative outcomes

- Frequencies of participants achieving resolution of CSA will be depicted by Kaplan Meier curves for the two ACPA-negative and ACPA-positive groups of CSA patients. Patients that develop RA will be censored at that date. Patients without this endpoint and who not develop resolution will be censored at their last visit in the study. Log rank tests will be performed.
- As explorative analyses on treatment efficacy within patients that developed the primary endpoint of RA: frequency of DAS-remission after 1-year and DMARD-free remission will be assessed for ACPA-negative and ACPA-positive RA separately. Data from DMARD-free remission will be presented in Kaplan Meier curves. To correct for the fact that RA-development may occur at different follow-up durations, resulting in different disease durations after RA-diagnosis, and consequently differences in the ability to achieve the mentioned outcomes, the time of developing RA will be set as time=zero in these analyses. Patients not achieving DMARD-free remission will be censored at the last visit or end of the study. Due to the expected

low number of patients developing RA, the difference between the treatment and placebo arms for these two outcomes will be presented/plotted but not tested statistically.

- Continuous outcomes will be analyzed with linear mixed models as described above with appropriate transformations, if applicable. Binary variables over time will be studied using generalized linear mixed models.

Sensitivity analyses

- A sensitivity analysis for the primary endpoint will be considered in which RA is defined similar as the primary endpoint (clinically apparent inflammatory arthritis with a clinical diagnosis of RA by the treating rheumatologist and either persistence during ≥ 2 weeks or prompt DMARD-initiation), plus adding the criterium 'fulfillment of the 1987 and/or 2010 RA-criteria'. [29, 30] The analyses (log rank, Cox regression) will be repeated by using this endpoint definition of 'development of RA'.
- The per protocol analyses will be presented as sensitivity analyses.
- Sensitivity analyses on the burden of CSA will be done including a correction for being blind for treatment allocation at 60 months (yes/no variable). At the time of unblinding almost half of the patients had completed 5-years follow-up. Participants were informed of treatment allocation; this correction will be included to evaluate a possible influence of this knowledge while completing the questionnaire at 60 months.
- Analyses of data of years 3-5 only. The data from the primary endpoint that is added in years 3-5 will also be visually inspected without the data from years 0-2. For the Kaplan Meier curves, the data are visualized in the life tables. For the data on physical functioning the data at year 5 will be evaluated.

Handling of missing data

Missing data will not be imputed for descriptive statistics. For analysis using Kaplan Meier curves, all data up to censoring will be included in the Cox regression model and log rank test. The data analyzed with the linear mixed models will mainly be studied under the MAR assumption (missingness at random).

Reasons for not completing questionnaires at 60-months may in part be considered completely at random (MCAR) (e.g. no willingness to spend time for this trial anymore, personal matters). Baseline characteristics of patients with missing and non-missing 60-months questionnaires will be compared. If major imbalances should occur between these

groups, predictors for the missingness will be studied and these predictors will be added as covariates in sensitivity analyses.

Low sample size

The subgroup analysis of ACPA-positive patients contains less than uncensored patients after 2 years. Robustness of these analyses will be checked based on correlation structure of parameter estimates and random effects, residuals and model convergence. In case of relevant conclusions based on these analyses, resampling techniques (bootstrap) will be used to support the validity of the previous analyses.

References

1. Dumoulin, Q.A., et al., *POS0061 Interception of the development of rheumatoid arthritis by a 1-year course of methotrexate in ACPA-negative arthralgia patients at increased risk for rheumatoid arthritis: 4 year results of the TREAT EARLIER trial*. *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases*, 2024. **83**(Suppl 1): p. 454-455.
2. Niemantsverdriet, E., et al., *TREAT Early Arthralgia to Reverse or Limit Impending Exacerbation to Rheumatoid arthritis (TREAT EARLIER): a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial protocol*. *Trials*, 2020. **21**(1): p. 862.
3. Krijbolder, D.I., et al., *Intervention with methotrexate in patients with arthralgia at risk of rheumatoid arthritis to reduce the development of persistent arthritis and its disease burden (TREAT EARLIER): a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled, proof-of-concept trial*. *Lancet*, 2022. **400**(10348): p. 283-294.
4. Verstappen, M., et al., *Early DAS response after DMARD-start increases probability of achieving sustained DMARD-free remission in rheumatoid arthritis*. *Arthritis Res Ther*, 2020. **22**(1): p. 276.
5. van Steenbergen, H.W., A.P. Cope, and A.H.M. van der Helm-van Mil, *Rheumatoid arthritis prevention in arthralgia: fantasy or reality?* *Nat Rev Rheumatol*, 2023. **19**(12): p. 767-777.
6. van Steenbergen, H.W., et al., *Characterising arthralgia in the preclinical phase of rheumatoid arthritis using MRI*. *Ann Rheum Dis*, 2015. **74**(6): p. 1225-32.
7. Krabben, A., et al., *MRI of hand and foot joints of patients with anticitrullinated peptide antibody positive arthralgia without clinical arthritis*. *Ann Rheum Dis*, 2013. **72**(9): p. 1540-4.
8. van de Stadt, L.A., et al., *The value of ultrasonography in predicting arthritis in auto-antibody positive arthralgia patients: a prospective cohort study*. *Arthritis Res Ther*, 2010. **12**(3): p. R98.
9. Feinstein, A.R., *Clinical epidemiology. 3. The clinical design of statistics in therapy*. *Ann Intern Med*, 1968. **69**(6): p. 1287-312.
10. <https://www.nhq.org/standaarden/volledig/nhq-standaard-artritis>.
11. van Steenbergen, H.W. and A.H. van der Helm-van Mil, *Clinical expertise and its accuracy in differentiating arthralgia patients at risk for rheumatoid arthritis from other patients presenting with joint symptoms*. *Rheumatology (Oxford)*, 2016. **55**(6): p. 1140-1.
12. van Steenbergen, H.W., et al., *EULAR definition of arthralgia suspicious for progression to rheumatoid arthritis*. *Ann Rheum Dis*, 2017. **76**(3): p. 491-496.
13. Mangnus, L., et al., *Magnetic Resonance Imaging-Detected Features of Inflammation and Erosions in Symptom-Free Persons From the General Population*. *Arthritis Rheumatol*, 2016. **68**(11): p. 2593-2602.
14. Matthijssen, X.M.E., et al., *A search to the target tissue in which RA-specific inflammation starts: a detailed MRI study to improve identification of RA-specific features in the phase of clinically suspect arthralgia*. *Arthritis Res Ther*, 2019. **21**(1): p. 249.
15. Boer, A.C., et al., *Using a reference when defining an abnormal MRI reduces false-positive MRI results-a longitudinal study in two cohorts at risk for rheumatoid arthritis*. *Rheumatology (Oxford)*, 2017. **56**(10): p. 1700-1706.
16. van Steenbergen, H.W., et al., *Clinical factors, anticitrullinated peptide antibodies and MRI-detected subclinical inflammation in relation to progression from clinically suspect arthralgia to arthritis*. *Ann Rheum Dis*, 2016. **75**(10): p. 1824-30.
17. Combe, B., et al., *2016 update of the EULAR recommendations for the management of early arthritis*. *Ann Rheum Dis*, 2017. **76**(6): p. 948-959.
18. <https://www.nvr.nl/richtlijnen/nvr-richtlijnen-standpunten-en-zorgpaden/>.
19. van Tuyl, L.H., et al., *The patient perspective on absence of disease activity in rheumatoid arthritis: a survey to identify key domains of patient-perceived remission*. *Ann Rheum Dis*, 2017. **76**(5): p. 855-861.

20. Krijbolder, D.I., S.J.H. Khidir, and A.H. van der Helm-van Mil, *To treat or not to treat? Current attitudes on treatment aimed at modifying the disease burden in clinically suspect arthralgia: a survey among participants of the TREAT EARLIER trial and healthcare professionals*. RMD Open, 2023. **9**(3).
21. Ten Brinck, R.M., et al., *Functional limitations in the phase of clinically suspect arthralgia are as serious as in early clinical arthritis; a longitudinal study*. RMD Open, 2017. **3**(1): p. e000419.
22. Schiff, M.H., J.S. Jaffe, and B. Freundlich, *Head-to-head, randomised, crossover study of oral versus subcutaneous methotrexate in patients with rheumatoid arthritis: drug-exposure limitations of oral methotrexate at doses ≥ 15 mg may be overcome with subcutaneous administration*. Ann Rheum Dis, 2014. **73**(8): p. 1549-51.
23. Gaujoux-Viala, C., et al., *Optimal methotrexate dose is associated with better clinical outcomes than non-optimal dose in daily practice: results from the ESPOIR early arthritis cohort*. Ann Rheum Dis, 2017. **76**(12): p. 2054-2060.
24. Bijlsma, J.W. and M.E. Weinblatt, *Optimal use of methotrexate: the advantages of tight control*. Ann Rheum Dis, 2007. **66**(11): p. 1409-10.
25. Smolen, J.S., et al., *EULAR recommendations for the management of rheumatoid arthritis with synthetic and biological disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs: 2019 update*. Ann Rheum Dis, 2020. **79**(6): p. 685-699.
26. Matthijssen, X.M.E., et al., *Enhanced treatment strategies and distinct disease outcomes among autoantibody-positive and -negative rheumatoid arthritis patients over 25 years: A longitudinal cohort study in the Netherlands*. PLoS Med, 2020. **17**(9): p. e1003296.
27. Wouters, F., et al., *Determining in which pre-arthritis stage HLA-shared epitope alleles and smoking exert their effect on the development of rheumatoid arthritis*. Ann Rheum Dis, 2022. **81**(1): p. 48-55.
28. Matthijssen, X.M.E., et al., *FRI0542 Obtaining high positive predictive values for the development of clinically apparent arthritis in patients presenting with clinically suspect arthralgia*. Ann Rheum Dis, 2020. **79**(872).
29. Aletaha, D., et al., *2010 rheumatoid arthritis classification criteria: an American College of Rheumatology/European League Against Rheumatism collaborative initiative*. Ann Rheum Dis, 2010. **69**(9): p. 1580-8.
30. Arnett, F.C., et al., *The American Rheumatism Association 1987 revised criteria for the classification of rheumatoid arthritis*. Arthritis Rheum, 1988. **31**(3): p. 315-24.